

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B281
Date: 02 April 2007
Take Off: 10:43:44
Landing: 16:06:35
Flight Time: 5h22m51

Campaign: VISURB

Operating Area: Round England, clockwise

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Jo Green	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Core Chem	Mo Smith	FAAM
8	Video System	Paul James	FAAM
9	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
10	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
11	Wet Neph / PSAP1	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Wet Neph / PSAP2	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
13	AMS	J. Crozier	University of Manchester
14	Video System 2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B281 Track 02-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B281
 Date: 02/04/07
 Project: VISURB
 Location: Round England - clockwise

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
094058		Start-Up	-.12 kft	125	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
103530		ASP	-.11 kft	070	open
103656	103931	Pirouette 1	-.10 kft	201	
104344		T/O	2.2 kft	027	
105513	110608	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.09 kft	051	
110513		QNH	0.78 kft	095	1030
110608	115312	Run 1.1	0.09 - 0.16 kft	109	
111518		Point 40	0.08 kft	106	
112839		QNH	0.12 kft	181	1029
113041		Point 41	0.12 kft	182	
113709		QNH	0.12 kft	188	1028
114317		Point 42	0.27 kft	195	
114607		QNH	0.18 kft	234	1027
115423	115550	Orbit 1	0.71 - 0.67 kft	233	left
115622	115739	Orbit 2	0.72 - 0.91 kft	175	left
115823	115939	Orbit 3	0.82 kft	109	left
120008	120123	Orbit 4	0.76 - 0.68 kft	071	left
120139	120521	Profile 2	0.73 - 4.7 kft	044	
120214		Video	1.3 kft	048	tape change
120521	120634	Run 2	4.7 kft	056	
120635	120740	Profile 3	4.7 - 5.5 kft	055	
120812	120940	Run 3	5.5 kft	055	12:07:41
120940	121549	Profile 4	5.5 - -.32 kft	056	
121549	121733	Profile 5	-.32 - 0.11 kft	051	
121734	131359	Run 1.2	0.11 - 0.14 kft	222	
121823		Point 42	0.15 kft	221	
122946		Point 43	0.26 kft	247	
123350		QNH	0.27 kft	275	1027
124432		Point 44	0.21 kft	232	
125732		Point 45	0.18 kft	226	
131053		Point 46	0.18 kft	291	
131359	131645	Profile 6	0.14 - 3.1 kft	323	
131645	132637	Run 4	3.1 kft	322	
132637	133251	Profile 7	3.1 - -.36 kft	319	
132819		point 48	1.8 kft	322	
133251	133338	Profile 8	-.36 - 0.10 kft	326	
133338	143111	Run 1.3	0.10 - -.03 kft	325	
133444		Video	0.11 kft	329	tape change
133824		QNH	0.14 kft	319	1029
134048		Note	0.19 kft	330	ci above
134221		point 50	0.30 kft	340	
135058		QNH	0.08 kft	010	1031
141827		QNH	-.03 kft	017	1033
142804		point 54	0.02 kft	021	
143112	143616	Profile 9	-.03 - 5.0 kft	043	
143616	145512	Run 5	5.0 kft	046	QNH 1034
144300		Point 55	5.0 kft	081	
145512	145557	Profile 10	5.0 - 5.4 kft	079	QNH 1034
145557	150458	Run 6	5.4 - 5.5 kft	077	
150141		Video	5.4 kft	077	tape change
150458	150957	Profile 11	5.5 - 1.8 kft	076	QNH 1033
150820		Point 79	2.9 kft	118	
150957	151543	Run 7	1.8 kft	143	QNH 1033
151543	151803	Profile 12	1.8 - -.09 kft	127	
151803	154138	Run 1.4	-.09 - 0.04 kft	143	
151934		QNH	-.04 kft	142	1034
152339		point 80	0.02 kft	137	
153722		QNH	0.01 kft	147	1032
154138	155116	Profile 13	0.23 - 10.0 kft	147	
160635		Land	-.04 kft	213	

160928	161150	Pirouette 2	-.04 kft	025
161429		ASP	-.06 kft	309 closed
161503		Shutdown	-.05 kft	309 52'04.36N 0'37.48W

B281 Track 02-APR-07

FAAM Sortie Brief
(alpha version with input from Alan Roberts – updated 12:45L)

VISURB-UK: Assessment of aerosol properties related to urban visibility

Flight No: B281

Date: 2nd April 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on radiation

Location:

Over ocean areas downwind of major pollution sources. Preferred area: North Sea/Irish Sea. AMPEP points will be used as detailed below.

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred, but not essential.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer

AMS

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

SHIMS

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 11Z (12L).
2. Transit and FL110 and perform a profile descent at 1000ft/minute to 500ft to arrive at AMPEP point 87.
3. Perform a SLR at 500ft (wherever possible) heading clockwise around the coast. The routing suggested is AMPEP points:
87->40->41->42->43->44->45->46 (southern section)
46->48->50->54->55 (western section)
55->79->80->87 (eastern section)
4. If meteorological conditions permit, perform a series of banked orbits (e.g. 50degrees at 500ft) at a position determined by the mission scientist.
5. Recover to Cranfield.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B281

Date: 02/04/2007

Sortie Objectives: Sampling of urban visibility in a strong easterly flow

Operating area: A clock-wise circuit around England and Wales.

Weather: Hazy. Cloud-free in the south, some alto-stratus cloud in the north and some Sc over the North Sea stretching from Humberside to Teesside.

Flight Patterns:

On taxi, a pirouette was performed for BBR calibration.

After take-off at 10:50Z, a transit at FL110 was performed before descending to 500ft at AMPEP point 87. The profile revealed a strong pollution layer with a top at around 5000ft and carbon monoxide levels around 250ppb and ozone reaching 70ppb. The clockwise circuit at 500ft was started and a peak scattering of around $210 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ for the green channel was noted. The highest pollution levels were off the Norfolk/Suffolk coast indicating strong advection from the continent. After reaching point #42 a series of orbits banked at 50° were performed. These were cloud-free and there was significant pollution above. Conditions continued to be polluted around the coast. Some alto-stratus was noted close to the tip of Cornwall – the BBR and SHIMS data should be usable from the start of the flight to around 13:38Z. The aircraft hopped over Devon at 3500ft before making a profile descent to 50ft before recommencing the circuit at 500ft. During this northward leg up the Irish Sea there was variable amounts of cloud. The neph scattering decreased steadily as we headed north and the visibility became reasonable >20miles close to the Isle of Man. A hop across the UK was then performed across the Lake District to the east coast. A profile descent was performed, but this was halted at 2600ft (within the pollution) as there was a thick layer of Sc below. After 5 minutes or so, the Sc had thinned enough for a profile down to 500ft. Interestingly the pollution was far higher above the cloud than below it. The rest of the circuit was then completed to AMPEP point 87 before recovering to Cranfield. A second pirouette was performed upon landing. This will need to be checked carefully as there MAY be some Ci contamination.

Summary: VERY GOOD! High levels of aerosol and CO and O₃ throughout the flight.

Problems: Wet nephelometer did not zero properly – presumably because it got wet from operating at high level during the previous flight. This will need to be checked and possible work arounds found for operations at high altitude.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

VISURB

Flight No **B.281**..... Date **2nd April 2007** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					VISURB Flight ENE flow - continental pollution.
					Round UK flight
					OSO, 5kts at Cranfield
					Hazy - no Ci or Sc. Cloud-free..
					QNH 1030mb.
10:38	St Pirouette			start 205	Approx 10:37Z start anti-clockwise Pirouette.
		GL			Approx 10:40Z end Pirouette.
				End. 205	Good pirouette - no cloud.
					Visibility poor < 5 miles.
					Climb out to FL50 - FL60 ^{dust} FL50-60
					Hazy from ground to 5000ft.
10:55:13	PI	FL110		52°36', 0, 12E	Start profile descent
					Top of haze at 5200ft.
					Green sea = $210 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
11:06:08	End PI st R1.1	500 ft		52°54' / 1° 0'	No whitecaps.
					SID may see sea-salt
					~ 11:08 from waves on coast
11:12:00					CO ~ 250 ppb.
					O ₃ ~ 70 ppb.
11:15:18					Point #40
					Polluted at #40, then
11:28:31					Green scat dies from 300 → 200 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
11:30:41					Point #41

Mission Scientist's Log

VISURB

Flight No **B.281**..... Date 2nd April 2007 Name Jim Haywood..... Page 2..... of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:31:00					G B ~ 244, G ~ 205, R ~ 156 $\times 10^{-6}$ μm^{-1} Wind 8ms ⁻¹ / 56deg Force 4? Sea state.
~11:39					NO _x 40ppb Peak in neph → Ship track. H ₂ SO ₄ AMS
11:43:17.					Point #42. CO 336ppb O ₃ 35ppb B 360, G 300, R 245 $\times 10^{-6}$
11:45					Many ships.
11:53:12	End R1 R1				Profile up to 1000ft, for orbits. Clear above.
	St 01	1000ft	200		45° Banked orbit LWD.
11:55:55	End 01	"	200		SZA ~ 45°.
11:56:22	St 02	"	170		Sea state 4/5
11:57:39	End 02	"	170		45° Orbit LWD.
11:58:23	St 03	"	090		Quite hazy, but not as thick as Norfolk coast.
11:59:39	End 03	"	090		
12:00:08	St 04	"	040		
12:01:23	End 04	"			
12:01:39	St P2				
	End P2 St R2	5000ft			Still in top (can go to 5800ft)
12:06:34	End R2 St P3				
12:07:40	End P3 St R3	5800ft			

All free from Ci.
Good orbits

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...281**..... Date **2nd April 2007** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:09:30	End R3 STP4	5800ft ↓			Heading back #43 → #42. Hazy.
12:14:00					Shipping
12:15:49	End P4 STP5	50ft 500ft			Lowest 50ft affected by shipping pollution.
12:17:34	SR1.2	500ft			Close to #42
12:18:23		500ft			#42.
					Profile
					Lots of pollution close to the shipping.
12:29:46		500ft →			Point #43
12:42:00					Point #44
					Hazy, B 234, G 197, R 160 CO 261, O3 56
					Travelling down wind. Not much variability in O ₂ or CO
					12:30 → 12:55.
12:57:30		500ft →			Point #45
					Sea-state 4.
					Same turbulence here.
13:08		500ft →			Same Ci ahead & to left.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.281**..... Date 2nd April..... Name Jim Haywood Page 4 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:10:53		500ft			Point #46
					Ci to left, turning away. Will not affect radiation
13:13:59	End R1.2 St P6	500ft ↑			Point #46 → #48.
13:15:10					Heading over the coast
13:16:45	St R2.1 End P6	3500ft →			Some turbulence during this run.
13:26:17	End R1.1 St P7	3500ft ↓	319		
13:28:19					Point #48
					Sea-state 5/6
					W/S 18ms ⁻¹ at surface
	End P7 St P8	50ft ✓	329		
13:38:38	End R1.3 St P7	500ft			Some As above & to North. Not affecting BBRs.
13:38					<u>Stop using BBR</u> upper data
13:42:20					Point #50
					Windspeed 21ms ⁻¹ 43°
13:50:00					BBR data definitely low.
14:13:00					Peaks in NO _x / NO ₂ → probably due to ships.
14:22:00		500ft →			Visibility dramatically better Green scat ~ 115 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
14:27		500ft →			Green scat level ~ 90 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹ .
14:28:04					Point #54
14:31:11	End R1.3 St P9	500ft ↑			Windspeed 2ms ⁻¹ 330°.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.281**..... Date **2nd April**..... Name **Jim Heywood** Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:36:	<u>End P</u> St R	FL50 →			4/8 As. Much more cloud to N.
14:43		FL50 →			Point #55.
14:45					Cleaner over Lake District.
14:50		FL50 →			Into top of pollution - being driven around the Lakes.
14:55:12		FL50 ↑			ATC.
14:55:57		FL60 →			Adjust to 6000ft. A couple of Cu below. Clear above.
14:59:00					Some heather burning in Pennines. Didn't penetrate smoke plume.
15:00					Some Cu below - look as though there's to pollution overlying the cloud. SWS & ARIES Nadir.
15:04:58	<u>End R6</u> St P11	FL60 ↓	77		Cloud below. Top of aerosol at FL40.
15:08:07					Point #79.
15:09:57	<u>End P11</u> St R7	2600ft			Sc below. 4/8 As above.
15:15:43	<u>End R7</u> St P12	2600ft ↓			Sc thinning.
15:18:03	<u>End P12</u> St R14	Scft			Below Sc. Pollution trapped ABOVE cloud → quite clean below.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 281

Date:08/30/07	Operator:MAP	DRS Time:09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 4
---------------	--------------	-------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:55:13	60	0.07	5	1												Start Profile 1 from FL110	
10:56:33	80	0.07		1												FL100	
10:57:35	90	0.07		1												FL090	
10:58:30	110	0.07		1												FL080	
10:59:25	90	0.07		1												FL070	
11:00:26	130	0.08		2												FL060	
11:01:25	1900	0.11		10												FL050	
11:02:24	1900	0.11	5	10												FL040	
11:03:22	2200	0.11		10												FL030	
11:04:08	2350	0.11		5												FL020	
11:05:02	2600	0.11		5												FL010	
11:06:09	2750	0.11		10												End of Profile 1 & start Run 1.1 @ 500'	
11:07:00	2250	0.11		5													
11:09:00	2000	0.11		100													
11:11:00	2175	0.11		10													
11:13:00	2175	0.11	6	10													
11:15:00	2300	0.11	7	10													
11:17:00	2200	0.11		10													
11:19:00	2300	0.11		10													
11:21:00	2400	0.11		10													
11:23:00	2200	0.10		10													
11:25:00	2300	0.10	8	10													
11:27:00	2200	0.10	140	10												FFSSP due to signal level too sensitive	
11:29:00	2165	0.10		10													
11:31:00	2160	0.10		10													
11:33:00	2100	0.10		10													
11:35:00	2140	0.10	141	10													
11:37:00	2165	0.10		10													
11:39:00	2240	0.10		10													
11:41:00	2100	0.10		10												11:40:00 24000 on pcasp	
11:43:00	2800	0.10	142	10													
11:45:00	2700	0.10		15													
11:47:00	1800	0.10		10													
11:49:00	1880	0.10		10													
11:51:00	3000	0.09	143	10													
11:53:00	2150	0.09		10													
11:53:15																End of Run 1.1	
11:54:33																Start Orbits @ 1000'	
12:01:32																End of Orbits	
12:01:44	1300	0.09	144	10												Star Profile 2 from 1000'	
12:02:53	1355	0.09		10												2000'	
12:03:42	1200	0.09		10												3000'	
12:04:44	950	0.09	145	10												4000'	
12:05:21	750	0.09		10												End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ 5000'	
12:06:00	900	0.09		10													
12:06:38																End of Run 2 & start Profile 3 from 5000'	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 281

Date:08/30/07	Operator:MAP	DRS Time:09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 4
---------------	--------------	-------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:07:41	650	0.09	145	10												End of Profile 3 & Start Run 3 @ 5000'	
12:09:00	740	0.10		10													
12:09:41																End of Run 3 & Start Profile 4	
12:10:25	950	0.09	146	10												5000'	
12:11:30	1400	0.09		10												4000'	
12:12:23	1800	0.09		10												3000'	
12:13:22	1800	0.09		10												2000'	
12:14:17	2260	0.10		10												1000'	
12:15:50	4000	0.10														End of Profile 4 & 50'	
12:17:47																Start Run 1.2 @ 500'	
12:18:00	2800	0.10	147	10													
12:20:00	3000	0.10		10													
12:22:00	2100	0.10	148	10													
12:24:00	2000	0.10		10													
12:26:00	1700	0.10		10													
12:28:00	1700	0.10		10													
12:30:00	1750	0.09		10													
12:32:00	1800	0.09	149	10													
12:34:00	1950	0.09		10													
12:36:00	2300	0.09		10													
12:38:00	2300	0.09		10													
12:40:00	2260	0.10	150	10													
12:42:00	2100	0.10		10													
12:44:00	2070	0.10	151	10													
12:46:00	2075	0.10		10													
12:48:00	2100	0.10	152	10													
12:50:00	2200	0.10		10													
12:52:00	2100	0.10	153	10													
12:54:00	2260	0.10		10													
12:56:00	2270	0.10	154	10													
12:58:00	2400	0.10		10													
13:00:00	4000	0.09	155	15													
13:02:00	2600	0.10	156	15													
13:04:00	2300	0.10	157	15													
13:06:00	2300	0.10		15													
13:08:00	2300	0.10		15													
13:10:00	2400	0.10	158	10													
13:12:00	2300	0.10		10													
13:14:00	2300	0.10	159	10												End of Run 1.2 & start profile 6 from 500'	
13:15:05	1400	0.10		10												1000'	
13:16:10	1050	0.09		10												2000'	
13:16:46	1000	0.09		10												End of Profile 6 & Start Run 4 @ 3500'	
13:17:00	1200	0.09		10													
13:19:00	1500	0.09	160	10													
13:21:00	1200	0.09		10													
13:23:00	1500	0.10		10													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 281

Date:08/30/07	Operator:MAP	DRS Time:09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 3 of 4
---------------	--------------	-------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:25:00	1370	0.10		10													
13:26:39																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 7 from 3500'	
13:28:37	1600	0.10	161	10												2000'	
13:29:40	1650	0.10		10												1000'	
13:32:52	2300	0.10	162	20												End of Profile 7 & start Profile 8 @ 50'	
13:33:40																End of Profile 8 & start Run 1.3	
13:34:00	2100	0.10		10													
13:36:00	2000	0.10		10													
13:38:00	1900	0.10	163	10													
13:40:00	1900	0.10		10													
13:42:00	1800	0.10		10													
13:44:00	1800	0.10	164	10													
13:46:00	1800	0.10		10													
13:48:00	1860	0.10		10													
13:50:00	1880	0.10	165	10													
13:52:00	1750	0.10		10													
13:54:00	1800	0.10		10													
13:56:00	1800	0.10		10													
13:58:00	1800	0.10		10													
14:00:00	1850	0.10	166	10													
14:02:00	1850	0.10		10													
14:04:00	1880	0.10		10													
14:06:00	1880	0.10		10													
14:08:00	1900	0.10	167	10													
14:10:00	1680	0.10		10													
14:12:00	1850	0.10		10													
14:14:00	1800	0.10	168	10													
14:16:00	1800	0.10		10													
14:18:00	1550	0.10		10													
14:20:00	1350	0.10		10													
14:22:00	1420	0.10	169	5													
14:24:00	1320	0.10		5													
14:26:00	1200	0.10		5													
14:31:13																End of Run 1.3 & Start Profile 9 from 500'	
14:32:18	850	0.10		5												FL010	
14:33:20	660	0.10		2												FL020	
14:34:18	720	0.10		2												FL030	
14:35:30	90	0.09		1												FL040	
14:36:19	210	0.09		1												End of Profile 9 & Start Run 5 @ FL050	
14:37:00	200	0.09		1													
14:39:00	280	0.09		1													
14:41:00	150	0.09	170	1													
14:43:00	120	0.09		1													
14:45:00	185	0.08		1													
14:47:00	130	0.07		1													
14:49:00	90	0.08		1													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 281

Date:08/30/07	Operator:MAP	DRS Time:09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:	Page 4 of 4
---------------	--------------	-------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:51:00	800	0.08	170	1													
14:53:00	920	0.08		2													
14:55:00	350	0.09		1													
14:55:13																End of Run 5 & Start profile 10 @ FL060	
14:55:59																End Profile 10 & Start Run 6 @ FL060	
14:57:00	100	0.09		1													
14:59:00	100	0.09		1													
15:01:00	120	0.08		1													
15:03:00	200	0.08		1													
15:05:04																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 11	
15:06:48	1400	0.11		5												FL040	
15:08:04	1300	0.10		5												FL030	
15:09:59																End of Profile 11 & Start Run 7 @ 2300'	
15:11:00	1410	0.10		5													
15:13:00	1400	0.10	171	5													
15:15:00	1430	0.10		5													
15:15:45																End of Run 7 & Start Profile 12	
15:18:03																End of Profile 12 & Start Run 8 @	
15:19:00	420	0.09	174	15													
15:21:00	460	0.08	175	50													
15:23:00	530	0.09		40													
15:25:00	750	0.10	176	70													
15:27:00	900	0.10		50													
15:29:00	1100	0.10	177	80													
15:31:00	1230	0.10	178	100													
15:33:00	1200	0.10	188	50													
15:35:00	1500	0.10		10													
15:37:00	1600	0.10		5													
15:39:00	1530	0.10		5													
15:41:38																End of Run 8 & Start Profile 13 from 500'	
15:42:47	1550	0.10	189	5												FL010	
15:43:46	1400	0.10		5												FL020	
15:44:50	1510	0.11		5												FL030	
15:45:10	1000	0.11		5												FL040	
15:46:36	600	0.11		1												FL050	
15:47:36	40	0.11		1												FL060	
15:48:35	50	0.07		1												FL070	
15:49:25	45	0.07		1												FL080	
15:50:15	50	0.07		1												FL090	
15:51:17	60	0.07		1												End of Profile 13 @ FL100	
	PCASP flowrate = 1.25 CC/sec																
	Some PCASP ch1 noise approx 35/CC																
	SID2 not fitted																

B281_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:47:43.68 --- - - - -
09:47:43.68 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:47:43.68 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:47:43.68 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B281
09:47:43.68 --- - - - -
09:47:59.26 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:48:09.63 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:48:12.10 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:48:19.67 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:48:25.73 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:48:29.63 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:49:30.86 SWS - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:49:34.19 USH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:49:37.46 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 0ms.
09:50:03.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:50:03.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:50:03.18 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:50:04.52 LSH - - - - Idling
09:50:14.08 SWS - - - - Idling
09:50:14.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:50:14.39 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:50:14.47 USH - - - - Idling
09:50:14.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:50:29.63 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
09:50:33.43 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 250ms.
09:50:37.75 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
09:50:42.26 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:50:47.08 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:50:54.34 USH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:50:59.04 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:51:16.23 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
09:51:20.69 LSH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
09:51:21.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:21.99 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:22.49 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:26.57 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:29.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:32.99 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:38.95 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 0ms.
09:51:42.30 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 0ms.
09:51:49.60 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:51:52.29 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:51:57.38 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:52:08.84 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:52:10.06 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:57:48.76 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
10:02:32.21 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:02:37.22 SWS - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
10:20:25.29 --- - - - - *** No
10:20:45.46 --- - - - - *** No problems on start up
10:24:06.88 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 0ms.
10:24:12.45 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 990ms.
10:24:40.88 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 0ms.
10:24:47.83 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 990ms.
10:26:26.04 --- - - - - *** Signal drops out on 990 int setting
    (attempt to resolve 1000 int time
10:26:51.72 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:26:51.75 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:26:52.33 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:26:59.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:26:59.86 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:27:02.66 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:27:20.35 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:27:44.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:27:44.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:27:45.41 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

10:27:52.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:53.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:55.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:27.37	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
10:31:32.93	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
10:31:39.29	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
10:35:45.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head at 0 degrees
10:38:57.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** Pirouette
10:40:26.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 90 d
10:48:04.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to 6 degrees Fore for transit
10:48:16.26	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:48:29.63	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
10:50:26.57	LSH	-	-	-	0	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 0ms.
10:50:32.04	LSH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 990ms.
10:53:11.15	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 400ms.
10:56:26.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 1 10:55:13
10:57:13.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to 4 degrees F
11:02:48.79	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
11:02:55.31	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:03:12.59	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
11:04:06.65	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
11:04:26.23	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
11:06:27.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of profile 1 start of run 1.1 11:06:08
11:06:52.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to 7 degrees fore
11:07:20.74	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
11:07:43.46	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
11:07:51.00	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
11:08:01.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:01.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:02.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:09.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:10.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:11.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:39.78	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
11:09:58.33	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
11:10:25.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to 6 degrees fore
11:12:50.91	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
11:15:38.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** Point 40
11:15:41.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:41.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:49.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:49.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:52.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:36.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:37.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:37.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:44.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:45.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:47.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:00.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** Point 41
11:31:05.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:05.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:05.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:13.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:14.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:16.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:47.45	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:43:37.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 42
11:43:46.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:46.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:47.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:55.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:55.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:56.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:57.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:49.54	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
11:51:20.77	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.

11:53:15.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:15.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:16.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:23.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:24.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:26.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:44.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of run 1.1 11:53:12
11:54:56.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of orbit
11:54:57.84	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 300ms.
11:56:05.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of orbit 1
11:56:25.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of orbit 2
11:57:42.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of orbit 2
11:58:04.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of orbit 3
11:58:05.44	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
11:58:12.74	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
11:58:35.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** Ignore prev - this is start of orbit 3
11:59:45.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 3
12:00:10.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of orbit 4
12:01:27.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 4
12:01:54.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** Profile 2 to 5000ft
12:02:18.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 9 degrees fore
12:02:26.51	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
12:02:34.86	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
12:04:09.08	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
12:05:18.99	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:05:20.92	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
12:05:25.61	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
12:05:36.78	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
12:05:55.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** strat of run 2 12:05
12:06:15.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 6 degrees fore
12:06:28.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:29.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:29.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:34.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:37.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:39.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:05.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of run 2 start of profile 3
12:07:56.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 3 start of run 3
12:09:21.32	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:09:21.44	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:09:36.73	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
12:09:41.74	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
12:09:45.66	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
12:10:09.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 4
12:12:18.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head at 177 aft
12:14:44.98	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:16:11.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 4 12:15:49
12:16:21.49	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:16:25.27	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
12:16:29.94	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
12:16:34.76	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
12:16:46.04	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
12:16:49.22	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
12:17:16.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:16.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:16.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:21.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:27.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:43.45	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
12:17:48.30	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
12:17:55.91	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
12:22:27.44	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:22:34.72	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
12:28:33.34	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:29:51.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 43
12:29:57.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:57.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:58.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:30:06.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:06.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:07.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:07.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:58.98	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
12:37:08.74	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
12:40:25.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:25.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:25.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:33.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:33.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:36.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:36.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 44
12:58:00.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 45
12:58:06.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:06.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:06.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:14.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:16.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:45.58	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
13:08:52.04	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:11:47.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:47.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:48.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:55.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:55.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:58.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:06.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 46
13:14:25.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 13:13:59
13:17:01.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.3
13:18:02.58	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
13:18:14.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** over land
13:20:35.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:35.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:36.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:43.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:43.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:47.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:22:46.58	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
13:26:56.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile descent
13:27:40.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** over sea
13:27:46.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:47.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:47.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:54.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:55.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:57.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:30.62	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:28:57.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head remains at 6 degrees fore
13:29:06.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 48
13:30:32.13	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
13:30:42.75	LSH	-	-	0	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 0ms.
13:30:50.73	LSH	-	-	0	-	VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 0ms.
13:30:55.71	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 990ms.
13:38:06.84	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:39:54.40	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
13:41:11.41	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:41:21.71	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
13:41:26.71	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:41:57.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to nadir at mission scientist request
13:42:21.81	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
13:42:26.68	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
13:42:29.90	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:42:37.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 50
13:42:41.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:41.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:41.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:42:46.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:49.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:51.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:44:38.92	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
13:44:44.23	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:44:56.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:00.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:06.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:08.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:29.60	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:48:33.17	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:48:40.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:40.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:40.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:45.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:48.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:50.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:53.13	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
13:49:58.43	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
13:50:06.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:16.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:40.40	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
13:52:26.33	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
13:54:08.69	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
13:54:15.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:23.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:44.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:45.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:45.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:52.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:53.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:55.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:21.26	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:57:30.61	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
13:57:40.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:42.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:46.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:53.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:35.76	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
13:59:45.89	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
14:00:22.59	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:00:26.87	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
14:01:20.33	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:01:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:34.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:00.71	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:03:05.92	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
14:03:11.01	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:03:15.95	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
14:03:19.94	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
14:03:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:25.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:26.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:33.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:33.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:36.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:39.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** currently below approx 6/8 alto stratus
14:16:36.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:36.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:37.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:44.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:44.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:47.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:44.64	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
14:22:52.86	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
14:22:59.81	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
14:23:12.27	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:23:27.97	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
14:23:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:23:30.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:30.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:37.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:38.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:40.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:53.32	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
14:27:05.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:13.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:04.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 54
14:28:21.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:21.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:21.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:29.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:29.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:32.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:31:28.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile climb
14:36:30.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run
14:41:11.31	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:41:18.07	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
14:41:27.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:27.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:27.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:35.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:35.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:37.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:43:11.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** now clear of AS2
14:52:09.82	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:52:14.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:25.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:18.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 6
14:56:28.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:28.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:28.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:36.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:36.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:38.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:13.65	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
14:57:20.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:57:28.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:59.36	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:02:38.77	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:04:18.92	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:04:24.16	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
15:04:31.08	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
15:04:37.78	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 150ms.
15:04:41.15	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
15:04:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:45.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:45.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:48.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:53.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:55.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:04.18	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:07:08.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:11.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:21.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 79
15:10:40.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
15:12:04.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:04.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:04.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:08.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:12.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:15.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:56.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
15:16:19.69	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
15:16:24.59	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:16:29.94	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
15:16:34.69	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 990ms.
15:16:39.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:16:39.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:39.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:47.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:47.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:49.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:35.81	USH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
15:17:39.98	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
15:17:44.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:55.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:18:22.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.4
15:19:37.55	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
15:19:44.51	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
15:19:52.25	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
15:19:58.02	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
15:20:03.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:03.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:03.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:11.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:13.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:14.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:16.48	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:22:56.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** below increasingly thin sc5
15:23:18.81	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:23:22.97	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:23:29.89	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
15:23:33.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:34.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:34.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:39.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:44.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:44.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:49.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** point 80
15:34:30.81	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
15:34:35.11	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:34:39.40	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:34:43.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:43.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:44.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:51.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:53.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:54.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:46.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile climb
15:47:45.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:46.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:46.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:54.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:56.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:57.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:11.05	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:48:18.84	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:48:22.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:22.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:22.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:30.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:33.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:33.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:28.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile end of science
15:51:53.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:51:56.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:51:57.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:04.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:52:12.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:52:17.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B281

page 1 of

Date: 2-4-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VISURB - lap of England & Wales.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
ARIES	1 lap	top is poorly. flying w' ARIES-2.					
		1. Cal					1. Cal 60x1, 60x1, H
0938		recon. after time reset.					
094658	pan	120x1	2	0	71	24	OK Run time = 12:30 N
	Various script testing						2. VZ (300x1, 2, 1. Cal) x3
103305	Start pan	1. Cal	C	71	24		
104650	To dim	1. Cal	C	71	32		
104819	"	2. VZ	C	71	30		testing
110050		END 2. VZ					not target down to 69. & shutter closed to recover
	PI ↓						12:30 run
110624	R1,500'	1. Cal	C	71	31		
110730	"	2. VZ	C	70	31		T = 9, sea looks good.
1114				0	70	31	
1115	T ₃ @ 800cm ⁻¹ = 344, T ₆ @ 1500 = 344						(pic.)
112017	R1,500'	2. VZ	C	70	30		V. Occasional white horse.
112228	"	↓	-	70	31		Shutter closed for calls
112750	"	↓	-	70			"
	"Searching the horizon & can't see where the sky ends, & the water disappears into the air..."						
1131	Shutter open for call — targets OK.						
113327	"	2. VZ	C	69.5	30		Boat to stbd. (pic.)
1136	"	↓	-	71	31		Shutter closed for cal.
1137	Don't like the spectral Window T ₃ higher than H ₂ O on CO ₂ (pic.)						
1140	R1,500'	↓	-	70	31		Still no visible horizon
1144	Boats to stbd (pic.)						
114624	"	2. VZ	C	70	31		
115330	ERI.1	↓	-	71	31		Shutter closed during measurement & script terminated after cal.
1154	orbit						

ARIES flight log

Flight: B281

page 2 of

Date: 2-4-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VISAR B - Lap of England & Wales

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
120138	P2 ² A	1.cal		C	71	31	
120303	"	R0521	Z	O	71	31	
120525	R2	1.cal		C	71	31	
120714	R3,5800'	1.Cal		C	71	31	
120909	R3,5800'	1.Cal	N	C	71	31	
120942	P4 ↓	1214 35	N	C			open ship track
121441	"	1.Cal		C	71	31	
121734	500'	1.Cal		C	71	31	still no horizon
1219	R "	2.VZ	-	O	71	31	
1224	"	↓			70	31	passing Dungeness
1226	"	↓	-	°C	71	31	shutter closed for cal.
122945	"	↓		°C			point 43
123142	"	2.VZ	-		70	31	white cliffs.
1235	"	↓	-	°C	71	31	shutter closed for cal.
1239	"	↓	-	"	70	31	"
124314	"	↓	-	"	71	31	"
124728	"	2.VZ	-	O	70	32	
124740M	"	↓	-	°C	71	32	" , bit slower to open again.
125145	"	↓	-	"	71	32	"
1256	"	↓	-	"	71	32	"
125702	"	2.VZ	-	O	70	32	Waypoint 45, 1257 32.
130010	"	↓	-	°C	71	32	shutter closed for cal.
130420	"	↓		°C	71	32	"
130830M	"	↓		°C	71	32	"
130934	"	2.VZ	-	O	70	31	1 men → pt 46
131245	"	↓	-	°C	70	32	closed for cal.
131349	ER+P9	↓		O	70	31	continuing to measure.
131647	EP6,R4	↓	-	°C	71	31	R4@3500'. Shutter closed for cal.
1321	R4,3500'	↓	-	°C	71	31	"
132243	"	2.VZ	-	O	70	30	
132530	"	↓	-	°C	71	31	script ended

ARIES flight log

Flight: B281

page 3 of

Date: 2-4-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VISURB - lap of

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments	
13	P7↓	1329	N	C				
132906	P7↓	?	Z	0	70	31	Seemed to be finished?!	
133358	R1.3	1.Cal	-	C	70	31		
133502	"	2.VZ	-	0	70	31		
133640	"	↓	progress bar	?			- Seemed to loose plot	
133811	"	↓	-	C	70	30	.OK now. Shtr closed for cal	
1341		Script lost it. Aborted						
134257	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31	Waypoint 50	
134410	"	2.VZ	-	0	70	31	patchy cloud overhead.	
1345		Script lost it. CDH restarted. OK						
134653	"	2.VZ	-	0	70	31	Ci above.	
135007	"	↓	-	C	70	32	Shtr closed for cal.	
135403	"	↓	-	C	70	31	Shtr closed for cal.	
135520	"	↓	-	C	70	31	Ci more wispy (pics?)	
135816	"	↓	-	C	71	31	Shtr closed for Cal	
135930	"	2.VZ	-	0	70	31	cloud more claggy	
140136	"	1.Cal	-	0	71	31		
140318	"	360x1	N	C	71	31		
140625	"	1.Cal	C	71	31	31	Script lost it... aborted.	
140825	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31	Ci more wispy above.	
140952	"	2.VZ	-	0	71	31	Scnu	
1412		Script lost it - aborted.						
141320	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31		
141440	"	360x1	Z	0	70	31		
141740	"	1.Cal	-	0	71	31		
141855	"	360x1	Z	0	70	31		
142218	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31		
142339	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31		
1425	"	360x1	N	C	71	31		
1426	"	1.Cal	-	C	71	31		
143615	5000	1.Cal	-	C	71	31		

112141

Bits of cloud above

ARIES flight log

Flight: B281

page 4 of

Date: 4-2-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VISURB - deep of England & wales.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1438	5000'	360x1	Z	0	71	31	Much variation in TB, some odd!
144126	"	1. Cal	-	0	70	30	
144245	"	360x1	Z	0	70	31	
144552	"	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
144739	"	360x1	Z	C	71	31	Shutter closed first half.
145050	"	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
145204	"	360x1	Z	0	70	31	
145528	PAR	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
145556	R, 6000'	360x1	-	0	70	31	
1458	Restarted as did not start properly						
1501	6000'	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
150323	"	360x1	N	C	71	31	went over cloud.
Looking at things now in curves viewer - in flight TB is rubbish!							
1510	R7 ²³⁰	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
151144	R7, 200'	360x1	N	C	71	31	over Sc sheet broken at end
151456	R7	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	turn & PV @ 151548.
151805	EPR, SRI.4						
154142	R1.4, 500'	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	Sc above
152320	"	120x1	N	0	71	31	Sc breaking up, some higher cloud.
152431	"	"	N	C	71	31	
152534	"	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
1527	Aries CDA restarted in hope of "receiving" scripts. OK						
1532	Still cloud above.						
153550	R1.4, 500'	1. Cal	-	C	71	31	
153700	"	362. VZ	-	0	71	31	still haze & for Ci up there.
1540	"	↓	-	C	70	31	shutter closed for cal.
1542	ER, PA						run aborted.
					OFF	1547	

(Handwritten scribbles)

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B. B281**

 Date **21/4/2007**

 Operator's name: **J BOWLES + D. TIDDER**

 Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								Blue 3.88×10^{-4} Cr: 3.22×10^{-4} R: 2.49×10^{-4} (Total)
								B: -1.85×10^{-5} Cr: 1.05×10^{-5} R: 1.05×10^{-5} (Back)
								B: 5.70×10^{-4} Cr: 4.77×10^{-4} R: 4.23×10^{-4} (Total)
								B: -1.36×10^{-5} Cr: -7.21×10^{-6} R: -7.21×10^{-6} (Back)
								On ground tests ↑
11:02			12.2	24	38.2	↗	9	Temp chiller set to 30°
11:07		500ft	13.7	32.6	65.7	↗	30	" " " " 36°
11:12		"	13.8	37	81.4	↗	36	" " " " 40°
11:15		"	13.9	37	87.7	↗	40	" " " " 43°
11:19		"	13.7	30.6	93.9	↗	43	" " " " 45°
11:23		"	13.5	31.1	97.2	↘	45	" " " " 25°
11:32		"	13.3	25.9	62.2	↗	25	" " " " 35°
11:38		"	13.5	26.9	67.7	↗	35	45° plots (shows on some
11:43		"	13.6	23.4	97	↘	45	25° plots went a bit screwy
11:50		"	13.5	27	64	↗	25	" " " " " 45° - still no W:D plots
12:06		5000ft	11.3	24	98.4	↘	45	43° (Humidity got a bit high)
12:18		500ft	13.7	41.6	98.4	↘	43	25° RH on wet neph
12:29		"	13.3	22.6	63.1	↗	25	45° one up the wrong way!
12:37		"	13.3	35.0	96.1	↘	45	10° and negative values

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.281**.....

 Date 2/4/2007.....

 Operator's name: D. TIMMEMAN + J. BOWLES.....

 Page 2 of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
12:49		500ft	13.5	33.4	47.1	A _{45°}	12°	
12:59		"	13.3	35.7	94.3	A _{10°}	45°	
13:08		"	13.5	35.4	53.1	A _{45°}	16°	
13:16		3500ft	12.2	24.0	93.6	A _{10°}	45°	
13:26	P7	3500	12.4	22.6	49.2	A _{45°}	15°	
13:34	Run	500ft	13.2	29.8	93.6	A _{10°}	45°	
13:42		"	13.4	30.8	52.7	A _{45°}	15°	
13:52		"	13.2	26.6	94.1	A _{10°}	45°	
14:01		"	13.4	24.9	50.4	A _{45°}	16.5°	Cooler ON
14:13		"	13.4	31.1	95.1	A _{10°}	45°	
14:20		"	13.3	23.6	57.9	A _{45°}	19°	Cooler OFF (didn't help)
14:36	Run	500ft FLOSO	11.3	2.4	95.7	A _{10°}	45°	
14:47		FLOSO	11.3	6.9	34.5	A _{5°}	11°	
15:12		2000ft FLOSO	12.4	14.5	23.6	A _{10°}	5°	
15:19		500ft	13.3	33.1	37.6	A _{45°}	10°	
15:34		500ft	13.2	33.4	94.9	A _{10°}	45°	
15:41		500ft	13.2	18.1	50.0	A _{45°}	12°	
15:44		22	12.2	18.1	73.2	A _{15°}	25°	
15:51		FLOSO	9.3	0.0	46.9	15°	15°	Wet Neph Zero -

Flight:

B281

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 08/05/2007
18:33:42**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

04/04/2007 12:53:50

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B281

Date: 2 April 2007

Instruments

1. 30 cc noise in Ch. 1 of PCASP
2. Problem getting RH derived data on Mi.Sci. laptop
3. Mi. Sci. Having problems opening new derived data windows – problem solved
4. F. Man. Problems printing – problem solved
5. F. Man. Having problems opening windows, only 4 open – problem solved
6. Wet Neph probs with zeroing instrument pre-flight, growth seen during flight.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B281:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	12 Nov 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

8 (?) tapes on unknown view
? x ???ward Facing Cameras
? x ???ward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk

Forecast chart (T+36)
Valid 1200 UTC Mon 02 Apr 2007

Sunday 1 April 2007 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Monday 2 April 2007 12UTC

Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Sunday 1 April 2007 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Monday 2 April 2007 12UTC

Low, L+M, Medium, M+H, High, H+L, H+M+L clouds

Windrose

Key for wind direction & speed on windrose only:

30 degree sectors (000-030, 030-060, ..., 330-360)
 innermost circle only for wind direction
 outer circles are divided into 5 knot bands, with wind speed increasing outwards
 (eg. 0-5kt, 5-10kt, 10-15kt, 15-20kt)

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|--|---------------------------|--|
| 1% to 10% probability = | | 50% to 60% probability = | |
| 10% to 20% probability = | | 60% to 70% probability = | |
| 20% to 30% probability = | | 70% to 80% probability = | |
| 30% to 40% probability = | | 80% to 90% probability = | |
| 40% to 50% probability = | | 90% to 100% probability = | |

NO COLOUR KEY FOR BAR CHART

GLENS 2007040100 Station: 3797

Key for wind direction & speed on windrose only:

30 degree sectors (000-030, 030-060, ..., 330-360)
 innermost circle only for wind direction
 outer circles are divided into 5 knot bands, with wind speed increasing outwards
 (eg. 0-5kt, 5-10kt, 10-15kt, 15-20kt)

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|--|---------------------------|--|
| 1% to 10% probability = | | 50% to 60% probability = | |
| 10% to 20% probability = | | 60% to 70% probability = | |
| 20% to 30% probability = | | 70% to 80% probability = | |
| 30% to 40% probability = | | 80% to 90% probability = | |
| 40% to 50% probability = | | 90% to 100% probability = | |

NO COLOUR KEY FOR BAR CHART

GLENS 2007040100 Station: 3496

01 APR
00zT+36

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 200 – 1000m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $2.82e-06$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 0 – 200m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $8.58e-06$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 200 – 1000m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = 1.22e-06

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 0 – 200m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = 8.60e-06

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 200 – 1000m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $9.98e-07$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 0 – 200m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $4.52e-06$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 200 – 1000m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $8.95e-07$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 0 – 200m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $6.37e-06$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 200 – 1000m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $1.32e-06$

NAME version 816

Back Run Time Integrated Air concentration
From 0 – 200m agl
1100Z 02/04/2007 to 1200Z 02/04/2007

Maximum value = $2.75e-06$

EVUK71 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 02 Apr 2007 0700 UTC

Aerosol

Aerosol

At 12Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007At 13Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

Aerosol

Aerosol

At 14Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007 At 15Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

Aerosol

Aerosol

At 16Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007At 17Z on 2/ 4/2007, from 03Z on 2/ 4/2007

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100